

Key Facts

Duration: January 2025 – June 2026

EU Contribution: € 2.488.140,55 (75,5%)

Programme: Digital Europe Programme

The Consortium

Coordinator: Cyber Security Ltd

Partners: A consortium of nine partners from seven EU Member States, including SMEs, one Competence Centre and two National Authorities.

The Challenge

The rise of Smart Manufacturing, Industry 4.0, and Digital Twins brings significant opportunities but also increases cybersecurity risks due to greater interconnectivity. The EU's Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) establishes a harmonised framework to address this, but navigating compliance can be complex and costly, especially for smaller companies.

CURIUM's primary objective is to support the implementation of the CRA by developing the Compliance Continuum, a suite of cybersecurity, focused tools and services designed to facilitate security testing, regulatory compliance, and risk mitigation for hardware and software products with digital elements.

The Mission

The project's vision is a more secure and resilient digital landscape where compliance is accessible to all. By simplifying and automating the process, CURIUM empowers European SMEs to build security into their products from the start. Its core mission is delivered through the novel Compliance Continuum, which provides:

- Information & guidance: clear direction on CRA requirements.
- Trustworthy security testing: tools for Self-Assessment and preparation for third-party certification.
- Streamlined compliance: automation to reduce costs and accelerate time to market for secure products.

The Impact

The Compliance Continuum Portal <https://portal.curium-project.eu/>

- Innovative tool suite: developing a modular, cost-efficient, and freely accessible toolkit to automate CRA compliance checks and risk mitigation.
- Agile validation: utilising a continuous feedback loop through real-world testing to ensure the tools meet industry needs effectively.

Empowering European SMEs

- Reduced compliance burden: specifically targeting micro and small enterprises, the project provides affordable solutions for Self-Assessment, dramatically cutting the costs and complexity of certification.
- Faster time-to-market: by streamlining compliance, SMEs can bring secure, compliant digital products to market more quickly.

Knowledge, sustainability & policy support

- Capacity building: fostering knowledge and skills through dedicated training and resources to support widespread CRA implementation.
- Long-term engagement: actively involving industry stakeholders and policymakers in tool development and training to ensure the project's outcomes are sustainable and aligned with evolving regulations.